

JOB SATISFACTION OF TEACHERS IN SELECTED PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN PANGUTARAN DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the job satisfaction of the teachers in selected public elementary schools situated in the diverse region of Muslim Mindanao, Pangutaran district. This paper primarily aimed to delve into the relationship of teacher's profile with the level of job satisfaction of elementary school teachers in Pangutaran District. Specifically, the researchers were driven to find answers to these following questions: a) What is the profile of teachers in selected elementary school in Pangutaran district? b) What is the level of job satisfaction of teachers in selected elementary school in Pangutaran District? And lastly c) Is there any significant relationship of teacher's profile with their job satisfaction of teacher's in selected elementary school in Pangutaran District? The researchers used Mean and Standard Deviation as statistical tools in dealing with the three research questions mentioned above. SPSS or Statistical Package for Social Sciences was used in analyzing the data. The findings revealed that the null hypothesis is rejected in Job satisfaction in terms of the work itself and working condition and environment when grouped according to educational attainment, current position, and length of service and accepted when grouped according to age, gender, and monthly income. In the final analysis, teachers are more satisfied in terms of the work itself and their working condition when their profile is grouped according to age, gender, and monthly income while they fell less satisfied when their profile is grouped according to educational attainment, current position and length of service.

Keywords: *job satisfaction, teachers, supervision, profile, working conditions and environment*

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction describes the feelings attitudes or preference of individual regarding work. It indicates how content an individual is towards his or her work. Armstrong (2006) defines job satisfaction as the attitudes and feelings people have about their work. Positive and favorable attitude towards work indicate job satisfaction, while negative and unfavorable attitude indicate dissatisfaction. Accordingly, the teachers' job satisfaction is significantly correlated to their commitment to the institution and that teachers who are content with their jobs always get committed to the organization. Therefore, the satisfied feeling of the teachers towards their institution positively affects their performance, thus, contributes to school success as a whole. (Balla et al, 2024; Jupakkal et al, 2024; Isa et al, 2024 & Abdurahman, 2023)

Pangutaran District consists of 23 public elementary and 8 primary schools headed by 16 school heads under the stewardship of 1 district supervisor. Most of the head teachers, principals and teachers in-charge holds masteral units if not a master or doctor's degree. For the school year 2016-2017, the overall numbers of teaching and non-teaching personnel of public elementary and primary schools in Pangutaran District were totaled to 177. Of which, 118 are females and 59 are males which can be further specified into the position of 135 Teacher I, 15 Teacher II, 3 Teacher III, 3 Master Teacher I, 1 Head Teacher III, 11 Principal I, 1 Principal II, 3 Teachers in-Charge, 3 School Nurses, 1 Administrative Aide and 1 District Supervisor.

Public school teachers as with any other professions have to be satisfied or must feel the satisfaction in carrying out their job no matter where their place of assignment (Abdurahman & Omar, 2021; Abdurahman, 2024). Teachers in the far-flung island municipality of Pangutaran, Sulu must find job satisfaction wherein at par comparable to the other more accessible areas in Sulu. Job satisfaction in order to be acquired is motivated and developed by giving the school teachers at hand their basic needs, peaceful environment, just leaders and moral support from their school head. Job satisfaction is tied up with economic, social, and cultural conditions where the public-school teachers are assigned. Many experts said that job satisfaction has something to do or related with job incentives.

Satisfaction of the public-school teachers, along with the just leadership of school heads, effective teaching learning activities and high students' achievements is a hallmark of a well-managed educational institution; favorable attitudes are the product of effective behavioral management, the continuing process of building a supportive human climate in the school. According to Locke (1976: 25) job satisfaction is a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experience. It is like any attitude, which generally acquired over a period as an employee gives more and more information about the work place. Job satisfaction is a critical factor in organizational behavior it needs to be understood, mentioned and built with so many haunt organizations. This study is concerned with the job satisfaction of public-school teachers in Pangutaran School District based on the perspective of their personal experiences.

Job satisfaction of the elementary school teachers in Pangutaran school district needs to be assessed whether they are still affected with organizational culture given the curriculum, delayed release of salary, newly deploying order, and sluggish process of the promotion. Generally, teachers at the island municipality have experienced problem in the k-12 curriculum due to inadequate teaching learning materials. The indicators of dissatisfaction of teachers investigated included teachers' commitment to work. This research attempted to link the above indicators and the main factors under the study which included the factors influence of work environment on teacher job satisfaction, colleagues, job security, work itself, and supervision.

Despite their deprived of many privileges, public school teachers kept on reporting, however, it does not necessary mean that they are satisfied. It needs further investigation and thorough observation, Butuan (1997; 22) citing McDonald said that to be happy in one's work is a privilege which we might argue, is the prerogative of few rather than of the many. Everyone has the right of a rewarding and satisfying job. Thus, concern over whether people like their jobs, their freedom to express their feelings about their work, and their ability to alter destiny through work are not parts of our tradition. According to Abdurahman et al (2024) that people clearly experience varying degrees of job satisfaction in their work according to the degree of their relationship with their upper level managers.

Moreover, this study sought to answer the level of job satisfaction of the faculty members of Pangutaran District, MBHTE, Sulu, Philippines. This investigation further give a baseline data for the school administrators and teachers to improve their performance in the academic playing field.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship of teacher's profile with the level of job satisfaction of elementary school teachers in Pangutaran District. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of teachers in selected elementary school in Pangutaran district?
2. What is the level of job satisfaction of teachers in selected elementary school in Pangutaran District?
3. Is there any significant relationship of teacher's profile with their job satisfaction of teachers in selected elementary school in Pangutaran District?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The setting of the study was conducted at diverse region of Muslim Mindanao, the Pangutaran District. The Pangutaran District consists of 23 public elementary and 8 primary schools headed by 16 school heads under the stewardship of 1 district

supervisor. Most of the head teachers, principals and teachers in-charge holds masteral units if not a master or doctor's degree. For the school year 2016-2017, the overall numbers of teaching and non-teaching personnel of public elementary and primary schools in Pangutaran District were totaled to 177.

Sampling Method

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. Moreover, this study used descriptive research method. Descriptive method is scientific research involved in determining the description of the characteristics or attributes of the subject and the interaction of these characteristics with other environmental linkages.

Research Instrument

The study will utilize survey questionnaire. The first section that measured personal information, 50 items in five categories measured the key variables using a standard degree with 51-100% satisfied = 5 column VS, 1-50% satisfied = 4 column S, neither satisfied nor dissatisfied = 3 column U, 1-50% dissatisfied = 2 column D, and dissatisfied = 1 column VD. Teachers of the Pangutaran Public Elementary School shall be the target respondents. Statistics will be used in the analysis of the data.

Statistical Treatment of Data

For the analysis of data, the researchers used Mean and Standard Deviation as statistical tools in dealing with these following question; a) What is the profile of teachers in selected elementary school in Pangutaran district? b) What is the level of job satisfaction of teachers in selected elementary school in Pangutaran District? And c) Is there any significant relationship of teacher's profile with their job satisfaction of teacher's in selected elementary school in Pangutaran District?

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on the job satisfaction of the teachers in selected public elementary schools situated in the diverse region of Muslim Mindanao, Pangutaran district. The participant of this study is delimited to the teachers in selected elementary school in Pangutaran district. The study is confined in the academic year 2020-2021.

RESULTS

Profile of Teachers in Pangutaran District

This section presents the answer to question number 1: "what is the profile of the elementary school teachers in Pangutaran District?" This includes the age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, current position, salaries and length of service. The following distribution were revealed: As to age, majority (36%) were below 25 years old; as to gender, Majority (68%) were female; As marital status, Majority (64%) were married; as to educational attainment, majority (44%) were having their bachelor's

degree; as to monthly income, majority (62%) have an income of below 18,999.00; and as to length of service, majority of the faculty members were only serving 10 years and below.

Table 1: Profile of Respondents

CHARACTERISTICS	Frequency	Percent
Age		
below 25	18	36.0
26-35	16	32.0
36-45	16	32.0
Gender		
Male	16	32.0
Female	34	68.0
Marital Status		
Single	18	36.0
Married	32	64.0
Educational Attainment		
Baccalaureate	22	44.0
With Masteral Units	16	32.0
Masteral	12	24.0
Current Position		
teacher 1	44	88.0
teacher 2	4	8.0
teacher 3	2	4.0
Monthly Income		
below 18,999.00	31	62.0
P18,000-24,999	19	38.0
Length of Service		
below 10	37	74.0
11-20 years	12	24.0
21-30	1	2.0

Level of Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Pangutaran District

This section presents the level of job satisfaction of among elementary school teachers in selected elementary schools in Pangutaran District. The statistical tool used

in this problem is Mean and Verbal description. In a normal distribution, the Mean is used to determine the arithmetic Average for the measure of central tendency and the verbal description is the interpretation label for each corresponding mean. Meanwhile, the level of job satisfaction of the public elementary school teachers in Pangutaran District are distributed as follows: They are satisfied with the nature of the work itself (mean=3.93) ; satisfied with the working conditions and environment (mean= 3.84); satisfied with colleagues in the district (mean = 4.19); satisfied with the school supervision (mean = 3.68) but they are undecided in terms of safety and security (mean = 3.41).

Table 2: Level of Job Satisfaction of elementary school teachers in Pangutaran District.

JOB SATISFACTION	MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
A. The Work Itself		
1. teaching inside the classroom the whole weekdays	3.94	Satisfied
2. preparing lesson plans and other required reports	3.98	Satisfied
3. dealing with problem kids	3.80	Satisfied
4. maintaining classroom and other facilities	4.04	Satisfied
5. identifying pupils' needs	3.84	Satisfied
6. implementing school policies	4.10	Satisfied
7. evaluating pupils' achievement	3.86	Satisfied
8. Encouraging open communications for effective delivery of services.	3.80	Satisfied
9. Clearly defined and logically structured job.	3.92	Satisfied
10. Participating in various activities in the school and community.	4.02	Satisfied
Mean	3.93	Satisfied
B. Working conditions and Environment		
1.The attractiveness of your surroundings	4.24	Satisfied
2. The cleanliness, sanitation, lightning, ventilation and temperature of classrooms.	4.16	Satisfied
3. The friendly atmosphere prevailing among people in the school	3.98	Satisfied
4. Availability of teaching modules and gadgets	3.34	Undecided
5. Adequacy and equity of equipment's and supplies.	3.24	Undecided
6. Performing varied tasks, parts of which are incidental and intervening in your regular functions.	3.50	Satisfied
7. Your job's involvement in societal development.	4.06	Satisfied
8. Living up to the expectations of the school and the community.	4.04	Satisfied
9. Having contacts with local public officials.	3.82	Satisfied
10. Well defined and prescribed daily routine.	4.04	Satisfied
Mean	3.84	Satisfied
C. Colleagues		
1. The congeniality of your co-teachers	4.44	Satisfied
2. The spirit of teamwork with co-teachers	4.22	Satisfied

3. The acceptance you get from people in your school	4.36	Satisfied
4. The personal and official concern you get from people in your school.	4.28	Satisfied
5. Working with co-teachers having equal educational qualification with you.	3.98	Satisfied
6. Working with co-teachers having higher educational qualifications with you.	4.08	Satisfied
7. Having local co-worker to work with	3.96	Satisfied
8. The way co-teachers get along with each other	4.16	Satisfied
9. Experiencing a feeling of common purpose with co-teachers	4.28	Satisfied
10. Genuine interest in learners' educational progress of co-teaches.	4.20	Satisfied
Mean	4.19	Satisfied
D. Supervision		
1. The way the boss handles his staff.	3.90	Satisfied
2. The competence of my supervisors in making decisions	3.78	Satisfied
3. Being kept busy all the time	3.68	Satisfied
4. The chance to work alone in the job	3.64	Satisfied
5. The concern of your superiors on matters affecting you officially and personally	4.00	Satisfied
6. The chances for professional advancement and promotion on this job.	3.04	Undecided
7. The feeling of accomplishment and appropriate recognition you get from the job.	3.70	Satisfied
8. Supervisor's role in the performance appraisal of teachers.	3.84	Satisfied
9. Frequent delegation of authority	3.68	Satisfied
10. Healthy working relationships existing among school personnel	3.60	Satisfied
Mean	3.68	Satisfied
E. Safety and Security		
1. The peace and order situation in your assignment	3.82	Satisfied
2. The accessibility and means of transportation to your place of work	3.20	Undecided
3. The condition of the school plant and facilities in terms of your safety.	3.70	Satisfied
4. The provision in the constitution for teachers in terms of tenure in the office means a lot of you	3.68	Satisfied
5. The nature of your appointment in term of your civil service eligibility.	3.64	Satisfied
6. The adequacy of the benefits and assistance exerted by the GSIS and PAG-ibig in terms of loans, Medicare, retirement and life insurance.	3.36	Undecided

7. The fairness and effectiveness in the promotion of teacher's welfare by membership to local and national associations/union.	3.16	Undecided
8. As a teacher you are doing at least as well financially, as you would probably be doing in some other job.	3.36	Undecided
9. Adequacy of pay in providing your personal and family needs	3.18	Undecided
10. Having ample amount left for recreation and vacations.	3.04	Undecided
Mean	3.41	Undecided

C. Relationship Between Teacher's Profile of Selected Schools of Pangutaran District with Their Job Satisfaction on the Work Itself and Working Conditions and Environment

Table 3 presents the relationship of elementary school teachers of Pangutaran District with their job satisfaction in terms of Work itself and Working Condition and environment. Moreover, the sig value are distributed as follows: Age ($p = > .205$ & $.455$); Gender ($p = > .345$ & $.095$); Marital status ($p = > .241$ & $.130$); Educational Attainment ($p = < .004$ & $.035$); Current Position ($p = < .005$ & $.041$); Monthly Income ($p = > .067$ & $.451$) and Length of service ($p = < .001$ & $.000$).

Table 3: Relationship teacher's profile and teacher's job satisfaction in terms of the work itself and working conditions and environment

Profile	JOB SATISFACTION			
	The work Itself		Working Cond & Environ	
	X ²	Sig. (2-sided)	X ²	Sig (2-sided)
Age	36.086 ^a	.205	35.300	.455
Gender	13.333 ^a	.345	20.000	.095
Marital Status	15.000 ^a	.241	20.000	.130
Educational Attainment	57.000	.004**	60.000	.035*
Current Position	40.00	.005**	37.333	.041*
Monthly Income	20.000	.067	15.000	.451
Length of Service	52.000	.001**	47.000	.000**

**Significant at .01 level of confidence

*Significant at .05 level of confidence

The data in table 3 showed that the null hypothesis is rejected in Job satisfaction in terms of the work itself and working condition and environment when grouped according to educational attainment, current position, and length of service and accepted when grouped according to age, gender, and monthly income.

The data suggest that teacher's combined contributions of educational attainment, current position and length of service have significant influence on their level of job

satisfaction in terms of work itself and working conditions. Hence, it can be deduced that teachers who only finished baccalaureate degrees, occupying teacher 1 position; and serving below ten years in the profession are still less satisfied and therefore, they still have high level of satisfaction on their present work and their working conditions in the school.

On the other hand, teachers' combined contribution of age, gender, and monthly income do not significantly influence their level of job satisfaction in terms of work itself and working conditions. This finding explicitly views that in spite of the teacher's age, gender and monthly income, they felt contented and more satisfied in the present status of their work itself and working condition.

In the final analysis, teachers are more satisfied in terms of the work itself and their working condition when their profile is grouped according to age, gender, and monthly income while they fell less satisfied when their profile is grouped according to educational attainment, current position and length of service.

Table 4: Relationships of Job Satisfaction in terms of Colleagues and Supervision Grouped According to Profile

Table 4 presents the relationship of elementary school teachers of Pangutaran District with their job satisfaction in terms of Work itself and Working Condition and environment. Moreover, the sig value are distributed as follows: Age ($p = > .305$ & $.381$); Gender ($p = > .172$ & $.220$); Marital status ($p = > .172$ & $.324$); Educational Attainment ($p = > .168$ & $.149$); Current Position ($p = > .060$ & $.103$); Monthly Income ($p = > .220$ & $.172$) and Length of service ($p = > .071$ and $p = < .040$).

Table 4: Job Satisfaction in terms of colleagues and supervision with the Profile of the respondents

Profile	JOB SATISFACTION			
	Colleagues		Supervision	
	X ²	Sig (2-sided)	X ²	Sig (2-sided)
Age	39.800	.305	40.000	.381
Gender	20.000	.172	20.000	.220
Marital Status	20.000	.172	18.000	.324
Educational Attainment	48.500	.168	56.000	.149
Current Position	33.107	.060	44.750	.103
Monthly Income	20.000	.220	20.000	.172
Length of Service	46.800	.071	52.200	.040*

*Significant at .05 level of confidence

DISCUSSIONS

This section discusses the profile of the respondents which incorporates the age, gender, length of service and educational qualification. Besides this also tackles the level of teacher's job satisfaction in the context of the work itself , colleagues, working

condition and environment, supervision, and safety and security.

A. Profile of the Respondents

In table 1, the statistical tools used in this problem are Frequency and percentage distribution. The profile of the respondents is measured using frequency in order to tally the number of times each occurs. The number counted and listed under the column entitled Frequency. The *percentage* distribution for a category is obtained by multiplying the relative frequency for that category by 100 to derive the percentage value of each category.

In the first category which is age, the age starts in below 25 has frequency 18 at 36%, age 26-35 and 36-45 has same frequency of 16 at 32%. It would mean that majority of the teacher respondents have ages that ranged from 25 and below. In the second category which is gender, the Male has frequency of 16 at 32% and Female has a frequency of 34 at 68%. Obviously, majority of the respondents are females. In third category which is the Marital Status. Single respondents have a frequency of 18 at 36% and Married have a frequency of 32 at 64%. It means that majority of the teacher respondents are married.

The fourth category is the Educational Attainment. Frequency responses testify that respondents with Baccalaureate degree has are 22 at 44%; those with masteral units are 16 at 32% and masteral has frequency 12 at 24 %. Therefore, Majority of the respondents have only finished their bachelor's degree.

The fifth category pertains to the current position. Frequency responses also testify that 44 (88%) of the respondents are occupying teacher I position. While 4 (8%) of them are teacher II, and only 2 (4%) are currently occupying teacher III position. The sixth category is the Monthly Income. There were two options answered by the respondents as follows: Below 18,000.00 has a frequency of 31 at 62%, and P18, 000-24,999 has a frequency 19 at 38%. It can be said that majority 62% of the respondents have a monthly income of below 18,000 pesos only. Lastly, the seventh category is the Length of Service. Below 10 years has a frequency of 37 at 74%; 11-20 years has a frequency of 12 at 24%; and 21 - 30 years has a frequency of 1 at 2%. It is also obvious that majority 74% of the teacher respondents are serving in the government below 10 years.

Corollary, Saner and Eyupoglu (2012) found that there was no significant relationship between intrinsic job satisfaction and age; there is a major variety in extrinsic job satisfaction among academics in regard of age. The result of the study showed that older educators are, in general, more satisfied than the younger ones. The findings of another study (Clark et al., 1996) has also showed that until an educator reaches the age of approximately 31, job satisfaction decreases and only after that age it increases. As for payment, what teachers care is rank and their ages rather than their genders and devoted holidays. In addition; as teachers get older, their satisfaction derived from their occupation increases (Guo & Wang, 2017). Besides, Shrestha (2019) conducted a study with 345 teachers and she concluded that older teachers display more job satisfaction, hence, they have more commitment to the job, leading the way to high performance.

As to respondents' gender, Ma and MacMillan (1999), found in their study that

gender and professional seniority were important in job satisfaction. According to this study, female teachers were more satisfied than their male counterparts. Seniority showed a statistically significant but negative effect on job satisfaction of teachers. Teachers who stayed longer in the teaching profession were less satisfied with their professional roles. However, contrary to his finding, in Luuk National High school, there are more male teachers (56%) as compared to female teachers (Asanji et al, 2024). This means that male teachers are dominant in this national high school.

When the job experience is considered, it is stated that teachers working for a long time were found to be happier with their jobs (Ogedengbe et al., 2018). It was also noted that duration of teachers' working years did not have any effect on job satisfaction (Fattah, 2010). Tye and O'Brien (2002) also stated in their work that even though the longer one continues teaching the harder it gets to quit the profession, teachers feel battered. It is also mentioned that newly-joining teachers affect the motivation of teachers who are already in the profession for a long time.

Moreover, Bivona (2002) states in her research that teachers who have at least ten years of teaching experience are more optimistic towards teaching. It is also found that experienced teachers majored in education while only some of the novice teachers did so as they thought majoring is a loss of time. Furthermore, it was revealed that teacher training and experience decrease teachers' stress levels, enable them to feel adequate.

B. Job Satisfaction of the Elementary School Teachers in Pangutaran District

B.1. Job Satisfaction in terms of the Work Itself

Table 2 showed the level of job satisfaction of the elementary school teachers in Pangutaran District. Generally, the teachers were satisfied (mean = 3.92) as to the nature of their work in the Pangutaran District. Specifically, the teachers show their passion in their chosen career. They are satisfied in teaching inside the classroom the whole weekdays, prepared lesson plans and other required reports. Satisfied in dealing interpersonally like kid's problem, identifying pupils' needs, evaluating pupils' achievement, and as well as on external matters like maintaining classroom and other facilities and have no difficulty in implementing school policies. Teacher aim to encourage open communications for effective delivery of services to clearly defined the logically structured job by participating in various activities in the school and community.

B.2. Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Terms of Working conditions and Environment

As to the teacher's working condition and environment, there were eight (8) questions have obtained the rating of "satisfied" and two (2) were rated "undecided" with a rating of 3.34 and 3.24 respectively and these are - on the Availability of teaching modules and gadgets with weighted and Adequacy and equity of equipment's and supplies. In other words, teachers are satisfied in terms of working conditions and Environment specifically in the attractiveness of surroundings, the cleanliness, sanitation, lightning, ventilation and temperature of classrooms and the friendly atmosphere prevailing among people in the school and because of it they tend to perform varied tasks

with well-defined and prescribed daily routine, parts of which are incidental and intervening in regular functions, and somehow the job's involvement will lead in societal development that contacts with local public officials and but is undecided in the availability of teaching modules and gadgets and adequacy and equity of equipment's and supplies. In a nutshell, the teachers were satisfied (mean= 3.84) in terms of their working conditions and environment in the same district.

B.3. Job Satisfaction in Terms of their Colleagues in the District

Gleaning from table 2, the teachers of Pangutaran District were satisfied (mean = 4.19) in terms of their relationship with colleagues in the workplace. Specifically, teachers are satisfied with the congeniality of co-teachers with a spirit of teamwork. In the same vein, they are also satisfied working with co-teachers with equal and higher educational qualifications that constitute a good working experience. They also felt satisfied of having a local co-worker to work with and get along with each other and experiencing a feeling of common experience with a genuine interest in learners' educational progress.

B.4. Job Satisfaction in Terms of Supervision of Their School Heads

It was generally found in Table 2, that the elementary school teachers of Pangutaran District were satisfied (mean = 3.68) in terms of the supervisory activities conducted by their school heads in the district. The data also justifies that the pattern of supervisory relationships between teacher and administrators or supervisors is satisfying. This is to say, that that administrator or supervisor can handle his staff well. The competence of supervisors is seen in decision-making and in proper delegation of authority which in turn leads to a healthy working relationship among school personnel. The teachers were also being kept busy all the time, were given the chance to work alone in the job and felt the concern of their superiors on matters affecting them officially and personally. They strongly agreed on supervisor's role in the performance appraisal of teachers but is undecided on the relation of supervisors in their chances for professional advancement and promotion on this job.

The finding is reinforced by Parker as cited by Doctora (1994) pointed out that satisfaction caused productivity. He further said that a happy person is a productive one. Thus, school administrators and supervisors should design a school environment which is physically, mentally, socially, economically and spiritually satisfying. This is likewise supported by Lowler (1994) in Jacoba (1994), who pointed out the satisfaction and productivity are in circular relationship wherein one effect the other. A person who is satisfied tends to be motivated to work and is productive. Corollary to this statement is that a person who is not satisfied is more or less not motivated to work and is less productive.

B.3. Job Satisfaction in Terms of Their Safety and Security

Generally, the elementary school teachers of Pangutaran District were undecided (mean = 3.41) in terms of their safety and security in the workplace. This means they are not sure whether they are safe in the their respective school considering that most of the schools in the said district are located in the island municipalities and prone to the threat coming from the instability of whether conditions and the like.

Specifically they are undecided on the following aspects namely : on the means of transportation; adequacy of benefits from the GSIS and Pag-ibig; On welfare and promotions of teachers; on other financial benefits and maintenance of the their family; and laxity of time to be spent for their family recreations and other activities. However, they are also satisfied in some other aspects such as; peace and order, educational facilities in the school, administrative policies and other civil service rules on tenureship.

C. Relationship Between Teacher's Profile of Selected Schools of Pangutaran District and their Job Satisfaction

C.1. Teacher's Profile and Job Satisfaction on the Work Itself and Working Conditions and Environment

The data in the table 3 showed that the null hypothesis is rejected in Job satisfaction in terms of the work itself and working condition and environment when grouped according to educational attainment, current position, and length of service and accepted when grouped according to age, gender, and monthly income.

The data suggest that teacher's combined contributions of educational attainment, current position and length of service have significant influence on their level of job satisfaction in terms of work itself and working conditions. Hence, it can be deduced that teachers who only finished baccalaureate degrees, occupying teacher 1 position; and serving below ten years in the profession are still less satisfied and therefore, they still have high level of satisfaction on their present work and their working conditions in the school.

On the other hand, teachers' combined contribution of age, gender, and monthly income do not significantly influence their level of job satisfaction in terms of work itself and working conditions. This finding explicitly views that in spite of the teacher's age, gender and monthly income, they felt contented and more satisfied in the present status of their work itself and working condition.

In the final analysis, teachers are more satisfied in terms of the work itself and their working condition when their profile is grouped according to age, gender, and monthly income while they fell less satisfied when their profile is grouped according to educational attainment, current position and length of service.

C.2. Teacher's Profile and Job Satisfaction on the Work Itself and Working Conditions and Environment

The data in table 4 affirmed that the null hypothesis was rejected on the perceptions on job satisfaction in terms of supervision when the data are grouped according to length of service and accepted when grouped according to age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, current position and monthly income. The finding reveals that, of among the independent variables, only the length of service is considered to be a significant predictor of teacher's job satisfaction in terms of supervision. It would mean that new and inexperience teachers still need to deal with their peers in the

workplace in order to have a smooth working relationship.

Meanwhile, teacher's combined contribution of age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, current position and monthly income do not significantly influence their level of job satisfaction in terms of supervision. It would mean that they already feel more satisfied on the supervisory process of their administrator in the school.

In the same vein, the null hypothesis is accepted on their level of job satisfaction in terms of colleagues when grouped according to age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, current position, monthly income and length of service. It would mean that the combined contributions of the independent variables above do not significant influence the teacher's job satisfaction in terms working with colleagues in the workplace. It is further noted that none of these variables to have significantly influence teacher's job satisfaction in dealing with colleagues.

In the final analysis, teachers are more satisfied in term of supervision when their profile is grouped according to their age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, current position and their monthly income. And they are also more satisfied in terms of working with colleagues when their profile is group according to age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, current position, monthly income and length of service.

Conclusions

Given all the findings and the data at hand, it is therefore deduced that; A) Majority of the elementary school teacher at Pangutaran District age 25 and below. More females than males and married. On educational attainment, most of them have only finished their baccalaureate degrees and few are pursuing their graduate studies and still occupying Teacher I position. In terms of monthly income, majority are only receiving 18,000 and below and serving in the government below 10 years. B) The teachers are generally satisfied with their present work, working conditions and environment, colleagues in the school district, and supervision. C) Teachers are more satisfied in terms of the work itself and working condition when their profile is grouped according to age, gender, and monthly income while they fell less satisfied when their profile is grouped according to educational attainment, current position and length of service. D) Teachers are also more satisfied in term of supervision when their profile is grouped according to their age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, current position and their monthly income. And E) they are also more satisfied in terms of working with colleagues when their profile is group according to age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, current position, monthly income and length of service.

Recommendations

In the light of the aforementioned findings, the following recommendations are hereby advanced:

1. Since, majority of the teachers are female, higher authorities should hire more male teachers to handle several co-curricular and extra-curricular activities like sports activities and the like.
2. The school administrator should look into professional promotion since majority of the teachers are occupying teacher I position.
3. The school administrators should be directed towards single focused- that is solely to raise the level of motivation. Because, teachers can perform better if they are intrinsically and extrinsically motivated. Thus lead to satisfaction in the workplace
4. Teachers should pursue graduate studies since most of them have acquired only baccalaureate degrees. This is to ensure the maximization of the professional and pedagogical knowledge.
5. Further research studies on job satisfaction must be conducted. Specifically, this writer highly recommends the following research titles:
 - a) Variables affecting Job Satisfaction and Performance of the Elementary School Teachers in Tapul District.
 - b) Determinants of Job Satisfaction of the Elementary School Teachers in Lugus District.
 - c) Determinants of Job Satisfaction of the Elementary school teachers in Jolo 1 district.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers hereby declare that an informed consent was obtained. In accumulation, the researchers assured that the information gathered from respondents are kept intact and confidential whereby all the data were kept in an archive where only the researchers can access. Ethical processes were strictly observed throughout the research endeavor in which the researchers have enjoyed their freedom to answer or refrain from participating along the process.

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